

A Derivation of the Gravitational Constant (G) from Other Fundamental Physical Constants.

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Abstract

This paper/submission/write-up seeks to present a simple derivation of the Gravitational constant, (G) in terms of some other fundamental physical constants. This is in line with helping with the mandate of the Committee on Data for Science and Technology (CODATA) in providing and maintaining a catalogue of self-consistent fundamental physical constants through its Task Group on Fundamental Physical Constants (TGFC). It is intended for the consideration of the TGFC, and the general scientific community.

Keywords: Derivation, Gravitational Constant, Physical Constants, Momentum, Conservation.

Background

The derivation depends on current (CODATA, 2018) values obtained from the CODATA and NIST [1] websites:

c : is speed of light in vacuum is : 299792458 m/s.

h : is Planck's Constant: $6.62607015 \times 10^{-34}$ Js

G : is Gravitational Constant: $6.67430(15) \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^3 \text{Kg}^{-1} \text{s}^{-2}$

α : is Fine Structure Constant: $7.2973525693 \times 10^{-3}$

e : is Elementary Charge: $1.602176634 \times 10^{-19}$ C

μ_0 : is Vacuum Magnetic Permeability Constant: $1.25663706212 \times 10^{-6} \text{ NA}^{-2}$

ϵ_0 : is Vacuum Electric Permittivity Constant: $8.854187128 \times 10^{-19} \text{ Fm}^{-1}$

Conservation of Momentum in Space-time Fabric/Aether.

According to Sir Albert Einstein, "The velocity of a wave is proportional to the square root of the elastic forces which cause [its] propagation, and inversely proportional to the mass of the aether moved by these forces." [2][3]. Therefore, if self-consistency is pursued or sought for amongst physical constants, the momentum of the Aether or the fabric of a given space-time ought always to be conserved, that is, constantly equal or set to unity in any direction of the space-time medium. Then, if m is the mass of a unit mass of space-time fabric or Aether, [3] and c , is the speed permissible by the space-time medium, then its momentum, p , is given as:

$$p = mc \quad (1)$$

$$p = 1 \quad (2)$$

$$mc = 1 \text{ Kgms}^{-1} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{If } c = 299792458 \text{ m/s; } \quad (4)$$

Then m , the unit mass of the fabric of space-time/Aether will be given as:

$$m = 3.335640952 \times 10^{-9} \text{ Kg} \quad (5)$$

The Planck Force [4]

The Planck force, $F = \frac{c^4}{G}$ (6)

Using current NIST/CODATA (2018) values of G : $6.67430(15) \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^3\text{Kg}^{-1}\text{s}^{-2}$;
And c : 299792458 m/s , the value of the Planck Force, F is obtained as:

$$F = 1.210255292 \times 10^{44} \text{ N} \quad (7)$$

In this paper, the Planck Force is herein re-modelled as:

$$F = \frac{4(mc)^2}{e^2\mu_0} \quad (8) \text{ and/ or}$$

$$F = \frac{2c(mc)^2}{h\alpha} \quad (9)$$

where $mc = 1$ in both equations (8) and (9).

Using current NIST/CODATA (2018) values, the value for the Planck Force from both equations (8) and (9) becomes:

$$F = 1.240021855 \times 10^{44} \text{ N} \quad (10)$$

Therefore again, given that the momentum of the space-time, $mc = 1$, the Gravitational Constant (G) could be derived from equating (6) and (8) as:

$$G = \mu_0 \left(\frac{c^2 e}{2mc} \right)^2 \quad (11)$$

$$G = 6.514085763 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^3\text{Kg}^{-1}\text{s}^{-2} \quad (12)$$

and/ or

$$G = \frac{h\alpha c^3}{2(mc)^2} \quad (13)$$

$$G = 6.514085763 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^3\text{Kg}^{-1}\text{s}^{-2} \quad (14)$$

Also, equating Newton's Force to the Coulomb's Force;

$$G \frac{m^2}{\pi r^2} = \frac{e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r^2} \quad (15)$$

$$G = \frac{e^2}{4\epsilon_0 m^2} \quad (16)$$

Actually (15) and (16) are valid for Boson statistics for this paper.

For Fermion statistics,

$$\frac{Gm^2}{4\pi r^2} = \frac{e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r^2} \quad (17)$$

And

$$\mathbf{G} = \frac{e^2}{\epsilon_0 m^2} \quad (18)$$

From (3) ($mc=1$)

Given c is **299792458** m/s ,

Then m , the unit mass of the fabric of space-time/Aether is given as:

$$\begin{aligned} m &= 3.335640952 \times 10^{-9} \text{ Kg} \quad (5) \\ e &= 1.602176634 \times 10^{-19} \text{ C} \end{aligned}$$

From (16) which appertains to Boson statistics:

$$\mathbf{G} = \frac{e^2}{4\epsilon_0 m^2}$$

$$\text{Therefore again } \mathbf{G} = 6.514085763 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^3 \text{Kg}^{-1} \text{s}^{-2} \quad (14)$$

Results and Discussion

When the value found for \mathbf{G} in this paper ($\mathbf{G} = 6.514085763 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^3 \text{Kg}^{-1} \text{s}^{-2}$) is compared to the current NIST/CODATA (2018) value, ($\mathbf{G} = 6.67430(15) \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^3 \text{Kg}^{-1} \text{s}^{-2}$) there is a percentage error of -2.4% .

In a recent experiment [5] (“Dynamic Measurement of Gravitational Coupling Between Resonating Beams in the Hertz Regime”) by Dr. Jurg Dual and his team, a percentage error of $+2.2\%$ was obtained compared to NIST /CODATA (2018) value.

In this literature, the negative percentage error obtained (-2.4%) could be attributed to the observation that the fundamental physical constants from which \mathbf{G} is (herein) derived were all measured/obtained in pure Aether medium and hence indicative of the Aethereal medium space-time. For example, the speed of light c , measured in pure Aethereal medium (vacuum) is faster than in other media.

Conclusion and Recommendation

The approach employed in this paper is expected to generally enhance self-consistency amongst fundamental physical constants, especially those related to the Gravitational Constant, \mathbf{G} . In the near future a lot of rigorous and meticulous scientific experimental activities and procedures are expected to be performed to further corroborate the findings of this paper as and when enhanced technology is available for same.

References

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